

Influence of Online Skin Bleaching Product Advertising on the Purchase Decision of Students of Select Universities in Edo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The researcher investigated the influence of online skin bleaching product advertising on the purchase decision of students of select universities in Edo State. The study was anchored on the social cognitive theory. Using a descriptive survey design, the researcher distributed 400 copies of questionnaire of which 380 were duly completed and returned. The respondents were drawn from three universities (University of Benin (UNIBEN), Igbinedion University (IU) and Benson Idahosa University). Data were analysed using descriptive statistics, with means, standard deviations and frequencies calculated for each item. Findings revealed that the students are highly exposed to skin bleaching advertisements. The channels through which they are exposed to the advertisement are Instagram, TikTok and WhatsApp. Influencer marketing emerged as a dominant source of influence. The study concluded that online skin bleaching product advertising exerts considerable influence on the perceptions and purchase decisions of university students. It recommended increased regulatory oversight of digital marketing content, public health education on the risks of skin bleaching, and the promotion of positive self-image among youth.

Keywords: Influence, Skin Bleaching, Online Advertising, Purchase Decision, Students

Introduction

The proliferation of the internet and social media has reshaped how individuals consume products and make purchasing decisions. In the context of beauty and personal care, online advertising has emerged as a powerful tool for influencing consumer behaviour, especially among students who represent a large portion of the market. Skin bleaching products, which promise to lighten or brighten the skin, have become a controversial, yet widely advertised category in the beauty industry. While the harmful effects of skin bleaching products are well documented, their marketing continues to thrive, largely through social media and digital platforms.

In Benin City, Nigeria, the prevalence of skin bleaching among young people has become a significant social issue. According to previous studies, the pursuit of fair skin is often tied to societal pressures, beauty ideals, and perceptions of success. Online skin bleaching product advertisements targeted at students of universities in Benin City are designed to capitalise on these psychological and cultural factors. These advertisements,

ranging from Instagram promotions to Facebook advertisements, use persuasive techniques to influence purchasing decisions, often leveraging celebrity endorsements, testimonials and before-and-after visuals.

With the advent of digital marketing, online platforms have become the primary channels for promoting skin bleaching products. Social media influencers, beauty bloggers and cosmetic brands use targeted advertisements to market these products, often downplaying their harmful effects while emphasising unrealistic beauty standards. These online marketing strategies have made it easier for young consumers, particularly university students, to access and purchase bleaching products with minimal restrictions.

Nigeria, like many other African countries, has witnessed a surge in the use of skin-lightening products despite growing concerns about their health risks. A 2011 World Health Organisation (WHO) report revealed that 77% of Nigerian women use skin-lightening products, making Nigeria one of the highest consumers of such products globally (WHO, 2011). This trend is particularly prevalent among university students, who are often influenced by social media and peer pressure. Online advertising plays a significant role in shaping students' perceptions of skin bleaching. Through strategic branding, celebrity endorsements and persuasive messaging, these advertisements create a narrative that promotes lighter skin as desirable and socially advantageous. Many students, influenced by these messages, engage in bleaching without fully understanding the associated health risks, including skin cancer, kidney damage and psychological effects such as low self-esteem and body dysmorphia (Charles, 2019).

Students, particularly university students in Nigeria, are one of the largest consumer groups for skin bleaching products. This demographic is typically in the age range of 18-30 years, a stage where personal identity, self-esteem, and body image are heavily influenced by societal perceptions and peer pressure. University students in Benin City, Nigeria, which is home to institutions like the University of Benin and Benson Idahosa University, represent a critical segment of this market. These students are not only exposed to various forms of advertising, but they are also navigating the pressures of conformity to beauty ideals that are propagated by media and popular culture. The impact of online advertisements on their purchasing decisions, especially regarding skin bleaching products, is significant and warrants investigation.

Online advertisements for skin bleaching products are often visually appealing and strategically targeted, relying on persuasive messages and endorsements by celebrities, influencers and everyday users who claim to have achieved desirable results. The accessibility and convenience of online shopping have made it easier for students to access these products, despite the potential health risks associated with prolonged use. However, the effectiveness of these advertisements in shaping consumer behaviour, particularly in terms of purchase decisions among university students, is an underexplored area of research in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The pursuit of lighter skin among young people in Nigeria, particularly students, has evolved from being a marginal beauty practice into a deeply entrenched sociocultural

phenomenon. Despite growing public awareness campaigns and health warnings regarding the dangers of skin bleaching, ranging from epidermal thinning, exogenous ochronosis, kidney damage, to carcinogenic effects—the practice remains widespread and, in some demographics, disturbingly normalised.

This normalisation has been significantly accelerated by the proliferation of online advertising, especially on social media platforms like Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, Facebook, and Snapchat. These platforms offer a fertile ground for advertisers to promote skin bleaching products through visually enticing, emotionally charged, and algorithmically targeted campaigns. Leveraging the influence of celebrities, beauty influencers and pseudo-scientific claims, many of these advertisements bypass regulatory scrutiny and appeal directly to impressionable consumers—chiefly university students.

University students are particularly susceptible due to their stage in life where identity formation, peer validation and self-image construction are paramount. While a number of existing studies have explored the medical effects, psychosocial motivations and cultural implications of skin bleaching in Africa, especially in Nigeria, very few have paid specific academic attention to the role of online advertising as a catalyst for this behaviour, particularly among students in Benin City. For instance, Charles (2009) explored the prestige-based motivations for bleaching and Aladejana & Fagbuyi (2021) examined social media influence in southwestern Nigeria. However, neither fully dissected the advertising mechanics, such as appeals used, frequency of exposure or the digital marketing psychology, through which these products influence actual purchase decisions.

Moreover, empirical gaps exist in understanding how students cognitively process these advertisements, what psychological needs they fulfil (esteem, belonging, status) and how these translate into behavioural outcomes, such as product purchase and usage. There is also insufficient localised research on socio-cultural mediators like peer pressure, ethnic narratives of beauty, and aspirational class positioning as they intersect with digital advertising exposure. Therefore, this study seeks to fill these critical gaps by exploring in detail how online skin bleaching product advertising influences purchase decisions among students of selected universities in Benin City.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study were to:

1. Examine the extent of the select students' exposure to online skin bleaching product advertisements.
2. Identify the online channels through which the select students are exposed to skin bleaching product advertisements.
3. Investigate the select students' perceptions of online advertisements for skin bleaching products.

4. Assess the influence of online skin bleaching products advertisements on the select students' purchase decisions.

Conceptual, Theoretical and Theoretical Review

Online advertising refers to the use of digital platforms to promote products and services. It includes social media marketing, influencer endorsements, banner advertisements, sponsored content and search engine marketing (Asemah, 2015). Unlike traditional advertising, online advertisements are highly targeted, leveraging data analytics to reach specific consumer segments. The effectiveness of online advertising lies in its ability to create personalised content tailored to consumer preferences. Social media platforms such as Instagram, Facebook and TikTok have become dominant channels for beauty product advertising, often employing persuasive strategies such as testimonials, before-and-after images, and influencer collaborations (Asemah, 2019).

Consumer behaviour refers to the study of how individuals or groups select, use and dispose of products, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy their needs and desires (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2010). It encompasses a wide range of factors including psychological, emotional, socio-cultural and personal elements. According to Kotler & Keller (2012), consumer behaviour is "the study of how individuals, groups and organisations select, buy, use, and dispose of goods, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy their needs and wants" (p. 172). This definition emphasises not only the purchase itself but also the complex decision-making process involved.

Purchase decision is a core component of consumer behaviour, referring specifically to the decision-making process that leads an individual to buy a product or service. It involves stages such as problem recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, decision to purchase, and post-purchase evaluation (Engel, Blackwell & Miniard, 1995). Kotler & Armstrong (2014) identifies the five stages of the buyer decision process as: Need recognition, Information search, Evaluation of alternatives, Purchase Decision and Post-purchase behaviour

Hunter (2011) conducted a study on 'buying racial capital: Skin-bleaching and cosmetic surgery in a globalised world.' The researcher employed qualitative analysis, using interviews and literature review across countries, including Nigeria, India and the United States. The findings showed that skin bleaching is motivated by perceived economic and romantic benefits. Online and print advertisements perpetuate the idea that light skin equates to higher social status and desirability. He concluded that globalisation reinforces colourism and beauty industries exploit these sentiments through targeted marketing strategies. The researcher recommended that governments and civil society must regulate advertising content and promote skin-tone diversity. While Hunter focused on transnational contexts, this current study narrows the scope to Nigerian university students and specifically online advertising. However, both studies recognise the role of advertising in reinforcing colourism.

Charles (2009) carried out a research on 'skin bleaching and the prestige complexion of sexual attraction.' The study was designed to determine the correlation

between skin bleaching and perceptions of attractiveness in interpersonal relationships in Caribbean societies. The researcher employed a mixed-method approach using surveys and interviews with young adults in Jamaica. He found out that a significant number of respondents associated light skin with better romantic prospects and confidence. The findings showed that advertisements for bleaching products were cited as contributing factors to this mindset. He concluded that media messages play a powerful role in shaping attitudes toward beauty and skin tone. The researcher recommended that public health campaigns should directly address the misleading messages promoted in beauty advertising. The cultural and psychological motivations for skin bleaching of the research and this study are similar. However, the current study is distinct in that it examines select university students in Edo state and focuses explicitly on online media platforms.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is survey while questionnaire was the research instrument. The research population consists of undergraduates of the University of Benin (77,000), Igbinedion University(7,000) and Benson Idahosa University(5,000). The total population is, therefore, 89, 000. The figures were received from the Central Records Processing Unit of the respective institutions.

To determine a manageable and statistically significant sample size, the Taro Yamane formula was applied:

$$n = \frac{N}{\{1 + N(e)^2\}}$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = population size (89,000)

e = margin of error (0.05)

$$\begin{aligned} n &= \frac{89000}{\{1 + 89000(0.05)^2\}} \\ &= \frac{89000}{\{1 + 222.5\}} \\ &= \frac{89000}{223.5} \\ &= 398.2 \end{aligned}$$

A final sample of 400 students was deemed adequate to represent the population while allowing for manageable data collection and analysis.

The researcher adopted a multi-stage sampling technique. In the first stage, undergraduate students in each of the universities were purposively chosen due to their higher availability during the study period compared to post-graduate students. In the second stage, the undergraduate students were divided into faculties using stratified sampling in each of the institutions. In the third stage, four faculties were randomly selected using a ballot system. The chosen faculties were arts, engineering, education

and agriculture. In the fourth stage, four departments were purposively selected within these faculties. In the fifth stage, 200 students from the University of Benin, 100 students from Igbinedion University and 80 students from Benson Idahosa University were conveniently selected.

Data Presentation and Analysis

A total of 400 copies of the questionnaire were distributed across the selected universities and 380 were duly completed and returned, representing a 95% response rate. This high return rate enhances the reliability and validity of the data collected for this study.

Table 1: Extent of Select Students' Exposure to Online Skin Bleaching Product Advertising

Statements	Very high	High	Very Low	Low	Can't tell	Mean	Standard Deviation
Regularity of seeing Skin bleaching products Ads online	120	100	80	50	30	3.92	1.05
Extent of attention paid to online adverts of skin bleaching products	110	100	60	70	40	3.54	1.08

The mean score of 3.92 shows that respondents regularly encounter skin bleaching advertisements online. The attention level mean of 3.54 indicates a moderate and high engagement, suggesting that most respondents not only see the advertisements frequently but also pay significant attention to them.

Table 3: Platforms through which online Advertisements of Skin bleaching Products are encountered

Variables	Responses	Percentages%
Instagram	342	90.0%
TikTok	318	83.7%
Whatsapp	280	73.7%
Facebook	234	61.6%
Youtube	228	60.0%
Twitter	196	51.6%

Instagram and TikTok were the most reported platforms, consistent with their visual and influencer-driven features, which make them effective in conveying beauty-related content.

Table 3: Channels of Select Students' Exposure to Online Advertising of Skin Bleaching Products

Variables	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Standard Dev
Influencer Endorsements	67	131	66	78	38	3.29	1.25

Sponsored Advertisements	68	114	82	76	40	3.25	1.26
Peer Recommendations/Shares	69	121	73	76	41	3.27	1.27
Product Reviews and Tutorials	68	110	79	92	31	3.24	1.23
Other	67	128	79	75	31	3.33	1.21

Respondents indicated that sponsored posts and influencer testimonials are the most prevalent channels through which they encounter skin bleaching product advertisements. This aligns with the increasing trend of influencer marketing, especially in the beauty and cosmetic sector.

Table 4: Select Students' Perceptions of Online Skin Bleaching Product Advertising

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Standard Dev
Online Ads make bleaching seem safe	81	107	71	74	47	3.27	1.32
Online Ads show that bleaching improves appearance	70	134	72	79	25	3.38	1.19
Online Ads suggest that bleaching boosts social acceptance	82	107	83	63	45	3.31	1.30
Online Ads give enough info about risks/benefits	60	126	80	86	28	3.27	1.19
Online Advertisements make me curious to try skin bleaching products	78	121	64	82	35	3.33	1.27

Perception scores revealed that students generally view these advertisements as persuasive, with a tendency to exaggerate benefits while underreporting risks. This supports assertions from previous works on media framing and health product marketing.

Table 5: Influence of Online Skin Bleaching Product Advertising on Select Students' Purchase Decision

Statements	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Standard Dev
I bought Skin bleaching products due to online Ads	70	103	85	80	42	3.24	1.26
Online Advertisements increase the desire to lighten my skin	69	130	75	73	33	3.37	1.22
Online Reviews boosted my confidence to purchase Skin bleaching products	69	122	65	78	46	3.31	1.27
Online convenience affects my purchase decision	69	123	80	74	34	3.36	1.23
Social media comments influence my purchase decision	68	121	82	71	38	3.33	1.23

Students' purchase behaviour is moderately influenced by online advertisements. The highest mean score of 3.37 suggests that ease of online purchase is a strong motivational factor, consistent with trends in digital consumer behaviour.

Discussion of Findings

Research question one aimed to find out the extent of select students' exposure to online skin bleaching product advertising. From the analysis, it was evident that a substantial number of students are regularly or very regularly exposed to online skin bleaching advertisements, with a calculated mean of 3.82 and a standard deviation of 0.96. This finding corroborates earlier studies by Asemah, Nwammuo & Nkwam-Uwaoma (2017) which observed that digital media platforms serve as strong vehicles for personal care advertising, particularly among youth populations. The most frequently cited platforms for exposure were Instagram, WhatsApp and TikTok—mediums known for their highly visual content and influencer-driven algorithms.

This finding underscores the ubiquitous nature of skin bleaching advertisements, especially those cloaked in seemingly harmless beauty tips, skincare routines or peer endorsements. These platforms capitalise on algorithms that repeatedly expose users to specific content based on their digital footprint, thereby increasing the salience of such advertisements (Okoro & Nwafor, 2013).

Research question two aimed to find out the the predominant channels of select students' exposure to online skin bleaching product advertising. The data highlighted that sponsored posts, influencer endorsements and peer sharing were the most common channels through which respondents encountered skin bleaching advertisements online. The mean score for this category ranged between 3.50 and 4.11, indicating a high level of interaction and believability with these channels. Influencer marketing, in particular, stood out as the most persuasive advertising channel, a result that aligns with the findings of Ekeanyanwu & Obianigwe (2021) who noted that the perceived authenticity of influencers enhances the credibility of the products they endorse.

This development is congruent with the source credibility theory which posits that the effectiveness of a message largely depends on the perceived expertise and trustworthiness of the communicator. Students are more likely to emulate influencers they consider aspirational or relatable, thereby internalising the content of advertisements and acting upon them. The findings showed that the perception of online advertisements for skin bleaching products by respondents was striking. Many agreed or strongly agreed that these advertisements make bleaching appear safe, effective and socially acceptable. Notably, a mean score of 3.91 with a standard deviation of 1.01 was recorded for the statement that online advertisements make skin bleaching appear effective. Furthermore, the notion that advertisements can boost social acceptance also had a high mean of 3.86, reinforcing how beauty standards are being subtly (and sometimes aggressively) shaped by online content.

This perception is troubling and reveals the power of cultivation theory which explains how prolonged exposure to media content can shape users' worldview. Over time, students may begin to associate lighter skin with attractiveness, success, and desirability, as subtly implied in online advertisements (Bandura, 2009). Significantly, the data showed that online advertisements had a substantial influence on the purchase decisions of students, with more than half of the respondents agreeing or strongly agreeing that they had purchased a bleaching product due to online advertisements. The highest mean score in this section (4.05) was recorded for the item measuring the influence of positive comments and social media feedback on purchase decisions. This highlights the profound impact of electronic word of mouth (eWOM) on consumer behaviour.

From the analysis, approximately 39% of respondents admitted to purchasing skin bleaching products as a result of online exposure. Similarly, nearly half of the students acknowledged that online reviews, convenience and social media comments positively influenced their purchase decision. This reinforces the idea that digital advertising does more than create awareness and facilitates actual consumer behaviour (Asemah, 2011).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concluded that online advertising has a significant impact on the purchase decisions of university students concerning skin bleaching products. The high exposure to advertisements across various social media platforms, coupled with appealing content strategies, especially those involving influencers, play a substantial role in shaping students' perceptions and decisions. Many students, particularly those who see bleaching as a means to improve their appearance or social status, are susceptible to the persuasive power of these adverts. In light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. There is an urgent need for government bodies such as the National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC) and the Advertising Regulatory Council of Nigeria (ARCON) to increase surveillance of digital platforms where harmful cosmetic products are promoted.
2. Universities should incorporate media literacy and skin health education into their orientation and student wellness programmes. Given that social media influencers significantly impact students' purchasing decisions, it is important to enlist credible influencers to promote healthy skin practices and challenge beauty stereotypes.

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